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FedORKG: Accessing Federations of Open Research Knowledge Graphs

Philipp D. Rohde, Enrique Iglesias, Maria-Esther Vidal
1. NFDI4Energy Conference, Hannover, Germany

21.02.2024

Scholarly Communication

17th Century

Scholarly Communication

17th Century

21st Century

Scholarly Communication

17th Century

21st Century

**No major difference in scholarly communication
for at least four centuries**

Open Research Knowledge Graphs

From human-readable papers to knowledge

Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints

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Germany

ABSTRACT
Knowledge graphs have emerged as expressive data structures for Web data. Knowledge graph potential and the demand for ecosystems to facilitate their creation, curation, and understanding, is testified in diverse domains, e.g., bioscience. The Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) is the W3C recommendation language for integrity constraints over RDF knowledge graphs. Enabling quality assessments of knowledge graphs, SHACL is rapidly gaining attention in real-world scenarios. SHACL models integrity constraints as a network of shapes, where a shape contains the constraints to be fulfilled by the same entities. The validation of a SHACL shape schema can face the issue of tractability during validation. To facilitate full adoption, efficient computational methods are required. We present Trav-SHACL, a SHACL engine capable of planning the traversal and execution of a shape schema in a way that invalid entities are detected early and needless validations are minimized. Trav-SHACL rewrites the shapes in a shape schema for efficient validation and rewrites target and constraint queries for fast detection of invalid entities. Trav-SHACL is empirically evaluated on 27 testbeds executed against knowledge graphs of up to 1M triples. Our experimental results suggest that Trav-SHACL exhibits high performance gradually and reduces validation time by a factor of up to 28.93 compared to the state of the art.

CCS CONCEPTS
• Information systems → Semantic web description languages; Graph-based database models.

KEYWORDS
SHACL Validation, Quality Assessment, Knowledge Graph Constraints.

ACM Reference Format:
Mónica Figuera, Philipp D. Rohde, and Maria-Esther Vidal. 2021. Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints. In *Proceedings of the Web Conference 2021* (WWW '21), April 19–23, 2021, IJCAI, Inc., Slovenia, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442381.3442877>

*M. Figuera and P.D. Rohde contributed equally to this work as first authors.

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WWW '21, April 19–23, 2021, IJCAI, Inc., Slovenia, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442381.3442877>

Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints

April 2021 • 3 citations • Semantic Web • Mónica Figuera • Philipp D. Rohde • Maria-Esther Vidal

Published in: *Proceedings of the Web Conference 2021* DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442381.3442877>

Add to comparison

Add to timeline

Add to provenance

Add to contributors

Add to preferences

Category	Value
Applied templates	No templates applied
approach	Trav-SHACL
has research problem	Knowledge Graph Validation
method	Early Detection of Violations Interleaved Execution Query Rewriting
uses	SHACL SPARQL

Open Research Knowledge Graphs

From human-readable papers to knowledge

Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints

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ABSTRACT
Knowledge graphs have emerged as expressive data structures for Web data. Knowledge graph potential and the demand for access to facilitate their creation, creation, and understanding, is testified to diverse domains, e.g., biomedicine. The Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) is the W3C recommendation language for integrity constraints over RDF knowledge graphs. Enabling quality assessments of knowledge graphs, SHACL, is rapidly gaining attention in real-world scenarios. SHACL models integrity constraints as a network of shapes, where a shape contains the constraints to be fulfilled by the same entities. The validation of a SHACL shape schema can face the issue of tractability during validation. To facilitate full adoption, efficient computational methods are required. We present Trav-SHACL, a SHACL engine capable of planning the traversal and execution of a shape schema in a way that invalid entities are detected early and needless validation are minimized. Trav-SHACL features the shapes in a shape schema for efficient validation and revisits large and constraint queries for fast detection of invalid entities. Trav-SHACL is empirically evaluated on 27 benchmarks executed against knowledge graphs of up to 14M triples. Our experimental results suggest that Trav-SHACL exhibits high performance (up to 10x) and reduces validation time by a factor of up to 20.93 compared to the state of the art.

CCS CONCEPTS
Information systems → Semantic web descriptions languages; Graph-based database models.

KEYWORDS
SHACL; Validation; Quality Assessment; Knowledge Graph Constraints.

ACM Reference Format:
Mónica Figuera, Philipp D. Rohde, and Maria-Esther Vidal. 2021. Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints. In Proceedings of the Web Conference 2021 (WWW '21), April 19–21, 2021, ACM, Geneva, Geneva, France, 10 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3441087>

¹M. Figuera and P. D. Rohde contributed equally to this work as first authors.

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<https://doi.org/10.1145/3441087>

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Contribution towards
FAIR Communication

Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints

Public Web | Mónica Figuera | Philipp D. Rohde | Maria-Esther Vidal

March 2021 | DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3441087>

SHACL

Applied

Trav-SHACL

Knowledge Graph Validation

Early Detection of Violations

Interleaved Execution

Query Rewriting

SHACL

SHACL

Add to comparison

Prevalence

Timeline

Added on 22 Mar 2021

Added by Philipp D. Rohde

Contributors Philipp D. Rohde

FAIR Communication

Papers

FAIR Communication

Papers

Data

FAIR Communication

Papers

Data

Software

FAIR Communication

Leibniz Data Manager (LDM)

Semantic Research Data Management

Trav-SHACL: Efficiently Validating Networks of SHACL Constraints

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ABSTRACT
Knowledge graphs have emerged as expressive data structures for Web data. Knowledge graph potential and the demand for ecosystem terms to facilitate their creation, curation, and understanding, is testified in diverse domains – e.g., biomedicine. The Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) is the W3C recommendation language for integrity constraints over RDF knowledge graphs. Enabling quality assessments of knowledge graphs, SHACL is rapidly gaining attention in real-world scenarios. SHACL models integrity constraints as a network of shapes, where a shape contains the constraints to be fulfilled by the same entities. The validation of a SHACL shape schema can face the issue of tractability during validation. To facilitate full adoption, efficient computational methods are required. We present Trav-SHACL, a SHACL engine capable of planning the traversal and execution of a shape schema in a way that invalid entities are detected early and needless validations are minimized. Trav-SHACL reorders the shapes in a shape schema for efficient validation and revises target and constraint queries for fast detection of invalid entities. Trav-SHACL is empirically evaluated on 27 testbeds executed against knowledge graphs of up to 50M triples. Our experimental results suggest that Trav-SHACL exhibits high performance gradually and reduces validation time by a factor of up to 28.93 compared to the state of the art.

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*Figueroa and P.D. Rohde contributed equally to this work as first authors.

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ACM ISBN 978-1-4503-8112-0/21
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3428138887>

Trav-SHACL: Benchmarks, Experimental Settings, and Evaluation

This collection includes all the data and scripts necessary to reproduce the results from the experimental evaluation of Trav-SHACL at WWW’21.

The data is modified data from the [Lehigh University Benchmark](#). The collection comprises nine data sets of three different sizes:

- Small Knowledge Graph (SKG) models eight universities
- Medium Knowledge Graph (MKG) models 32 universities
- Large Knowledge Graph (LKG) models 256 universities

There are three data sets of each size. They differ only in those triples that link an entity to a university, i.e., the university the entity is linked to. This was done in order to achieve different percentages of valid universities when evaluating the SHACL shape schemas for the above-mentioned paper.

The data is available for download in Turtle format and preloaded for the use with Virtuoso 7.20.3229.

In order to reproduce the results reported, you will only need the archive of the scripts as the shapes are also included in that script and the data will be downloaded automatically.

Data and Resources

	rdf-turtle.zip data in Turtle format	Explore
	virtuoso-db.zip data preloaded in Virtuoso 7.20.3229	Explore
	shape-schemas.zip shape schemas used in the evaluation	Explore
	Evaluation-WWW2021.zip all necessary scripts to reproduce the reported results	Explore

Cite this as

Mónica Figueroa, Philipp D. Rohde, Maria-Esther Vidal (2021). Dataset: Trav-SHACL: Benchmarks, Experimental Settings, and Evaluation. <https://doi.org/10.25835/0035739>

DOI retrieved: January 20, 2021

LDM Knowledge Graph

Trav-SHACL: Benchmarks, Experimental Settings, and Evaluation

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- Small Knowledge Graph (SKG) models eight universities
- Medium Knowledge Graph (MKG) models 32 universities
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Data and Resources

 rdfl-turtle.zip
data in Turtle format

[Explore](#)

 virtuoso-db.zip
data preloaded in Virtuoso 7.20.3229

[Explore](#)

 shape-schemas.zip
shape schemas used in the evaluation

[Explore](#)

 Evaluation-WWW2021.zip
all necessary scripts to reproduce the reported results

[Explore](#)

Cite this as

Mónica Figuera, Philipp D. Rohde, María-Esther Vidal (2021). Dataset: Trav-SHACL: Benchmarks, Experimental Settings, and Evaluation. <https://doi.org/10.25835/0035739>

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LDM Knowledge Graph

Trav-SHACL: Benchmarks, Experimental Settings, and Evaluation

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The data is modified data from the Lehigh University Benchmark. The collection comprises nine data sets of three different sizes:

- Small Knowledge Graph (SKG) models eight universities
- Medium Knowledge Graph (MKG) models 32 universities
- Large Knowledge Graph (LKG) models 128 universities

There are three data sets of each size. They are linked to this page in order to reproduce the results reported, you will need to download the data, the scripts and the data will be downloaded automatically.

The data is available for download in Turtle format.

Data and Resources

- [rdf-turtle.zip](#)
data in Turtle format Explore -
- [virtuoso-db.zip](#)
data preloaded in Virtuoso 7.20.3229 Explore -
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DOI retrieved: January 20, 2021

The LDM Knowledge Graph is an Open Research Knowledge Graph

Open Research Knowledge Graphs

Keep the ORKGs **separate**

Open Research Knowledge Graphs

Keep the ORKGs **separate**

... or ...

Open Research Knowledge Graphs

Keep the ORKGs **separate**

... or ...

form a **federation** of ORKGs?

Query Processing

Federated Query Processing

FedORKG: Goal

Provide Insights

FedORKG: Goal

Provide Insights

Support FAIR Communication

FedORKG: Requirement

Links between the ORKGs

FedORKG: Querying

DeTrusty

<https://github.com/SDM-TIB/DeTrusty>

- Semantic Source Descriptions
 - RDF classes
 - Properties
 - Sources
- Star-shaped Decomposition

FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

PREFIX orkgr: <http://orkg.org/orkg/resource/>

PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>

PREFIX orkgp: <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/>

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>

PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>

```
SELECT ?paper_title ?research_field_label ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher WHERE {  
  orkgr:R576963 a orkgc:Paper .  
  orkgr:R576963 rdfs:label ?paper_title .  
  orkgr:R576963 orkgp:P30 ?research_field .  
  orkgr:R576963 orkgp:P31 ?contribution .  
  ?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label .  
  ?contribution <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/wikidata:P356> ?benchmark_doi .  
  ?benchmark datacite:usesIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_doi .  
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title .  
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher .  
}
```

FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

```

PREFIX orkgr: <http://orkg.org/orkg/resource/>
PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>
PREFIX orkgp: <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>
  
```

```

SELECT ?paper_title ?research_field_label ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher WHERE {
  orkgr:R576963 a orkgc:Paper .
  orkgr:R576963 rdfs:label ?paper_title .
  orkgr:R576963 orkgp:P30 ?research_field .
  orkgr:R576963 orkgp:P31 ?contribution .
  ?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label .
  ?contribution <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/wikidata:P356> ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark datacite:usesIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title .
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher .
}
  
```


FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

Result of the example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG

```

PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>
PREFIX orkg: <http://orkg.org/orkg/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/dcat/terms/>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX schema: <http://schema.org/>
PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>
PREFIX orkg: <http://orkg.org/orkg/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/dcat/terms/>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX schema: <http://schema.org/>
SELECT ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher
WHERE {
  ?benchmark dcat:usesIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title .
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher .
}

```


Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

SPARQL Queries

Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

SPARQL Queries

Ontologies

Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

SPARQL Queries

Ontologies

QA Systems

Challenge 2: Alignment of ORKGs

Establishing links between the ORKGs

Challenge 2: Alignment of ORKGs

Establishing links between the ORKGs

Add DOI of paper when adding dataset

Challenge 2: Alignment of ORKGs

Establishing links between the ORKGs

Conclusions & Future Work

 TIB

FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

```

PREFIX orkg: <http://orkg.org/orkg/resource/>
PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>
PREFIX orkgp: <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>

SELECT ?paper title ?research_field_label ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher WHERE {
  orkg:R576963 a orkgc:Paper .
  orkg:R576963 rdfs:label ?paper_title .
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P30 ?research_field .
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P31 ?contribution .
  ?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label .
  ?contribution <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/Wikidata:P356> ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark datacite:useidentifierScheme ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title .
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher .
}
    
```

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Virtual Integration of ORKGs

Conclusions & Future Work

FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

```

PREFIX orkg: <http://orkg.org/orkg/resource>
PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class>
PREFIX orkgp: <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>

SELECT ?paper title ?research_field_label ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher WHERE {
  orkg:R576963 a orkgc:Paper
  orkg:R576963 rdfs:label ?paper_title
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P30 ?research_field
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P31 ?contribution
  ?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label
  ?contribution <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicates/wikidata:P356> ?benchmark_doi
  ?benchmark datacite:useIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_doi
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher
}
    
```


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FedORKG: Goal

Provide Insights

Support FAIR Communication

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FAIR Scholarly Communication

Conclusions & Future Work

FedORKG: Example Query

FedORKG: Goal

Reduce knowledge required for benefiting from federations of ORKGs

```

?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label
?contribution http://orkg.org/orkg/instance/wikidata:P356a ?benchmark_id
?benchmark dcat:hasUsedIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_id
?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title
?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher
        
```

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Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

SPARQL Queries

Ontologies

QA Systems

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Conclusions & Future Work

FedORKG: Example Query

FedORKG: Goal

Establishing links between different ORKGs in order to profit from them

```

?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label
?contribution http://orkg.org/orkg/predicates/wikidata:P356a ?benchmark_uri
?benchmark dact:isUserIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_uri
?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title
?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher
        
```

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Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

Challenge 2: Alignment of ORKGs

SPARQL Queries

Ontologies

QA Systems

If paper not in ORKG:

- Fetch metadata
- Collect basic information
- Research Field
- Problem
- Contribution
- Solution
- Conclusions

Add DOI of paper when adding dataset

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Conclusions & Future Work

FedORKG: Example Query

Example query retrieving metadata from ORKG and LDM KG for a specific paper

```

PREFIX orkg: <http://orkg.org/orkg/resource/>
PREFIX orkgc: <http://orkg.org/orkg/class/>
PREFIX orkgp: <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>

SELECT ?paper title ?research_field_label ?benchmark_doi ?benchmark_title ?benchmark_publisher WHERE {
  orkg:R576963 a orkgc:Paper .
  orkg:R576963 rdfs:label ?paper_title .
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P30 ?research_field .
  orkg:R576963 orkgp:P31 ?contribution .
  ?research_field rdfs:label ?research_field_label .
  ?contribution <http://orkg.org/orkg/predicate/Wikidata:P566> ?benchmark_doi .
  ?benchmark datacite:useIdentifierScheme ?benchmark_title .
  ?benchmark dct:title ?benchmark_title .
  ?benchmark dct:publisher ?benchmark_publisher .
}
    
```

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FedORKG: Goal

Provide Insights

Support FAIR Communication

P.D. Rohde et al.: FedORKG 1. NFDI4Energy Conference, Hannover, Germany, Feb 20-21, 2024 22

Challenge 1: Knowledge Required

SPARQL Queries

Ontologies

QA Systems

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Challenge 2: Alignment of ORKGs

Establishing links between the ORKGs

If paper not in ORKG:

- Fetch metadata
- Collect basic information
 - Research Field
 - Problem
 - Contribution
 - Solution
 - Conclusions

Add DOI of paper when adding dataset

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philipp.rohde@tib.eu

